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A physics-based low-order filter approximation for scattering from a rigid sphere

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ABSTRACT:

Efficient simulation of object scattering is crucial in virtual and room acoustics, particularly for interactive scenarios where time-varying diffraction must be evaluated repeatedly in real-time. In this context, the rigid sphere is commonly used as a simple geometric representation of more complex three-dimensional objects. Although the analytical solution for rigid sphere scattering is well known, its computation is too involved for interactive audio rendering. In this paper, we propose a physically informed, low-order digital filter approximation of rigid sphere scattering for arbitrary source and receiver positions. For the low-frequency range, the first three terms of the spherical harmonics analytical solution are directly expressed by combined first-order low- and high-pass filters. For high-frequencies, the basic properties of rigid sphere scattering are approximated by modelling the shortest and longest paths reflected or bent around the sphere. Both approximations are combined using a blending function to obtain the wideband result. The magnitude of the low-frequency approximation matches the analytical solution well, yielding mean root mean square errors below 0.5 dB for source and receiver distances greater than twice the sphere radius and about 1.5 dB at smaller distances. For the high-frequency range, the mean error in magnitude is overall larger and is about 2 dB.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The sound field around a rigid sphere is well known and can be analytically described (e.g., [Beranek and Mellow, 2019](#); [Strutt and Lodge, 1904](#)). In architectural, room, and virtual acoustics, a rigid sphere has often been considered as a simplified geometrical body to model diffraction and scattering effects of small-scale objects in or near the sound propagation path, such as the human head (e.g., [Brown and Duda, 1998](#); [Ewert et al., 2021](#)). In this context, diffraction typically refers to the process where sound waves bend into the “shadowed” region of an obstacle ([Berg and Sorensen, 2018](#)) including corners and edges. Because of diffraction, the sound field remains continuous around the obstacle and exhibits frequency-dependent attenuation in the shadowed region, perceptually relevant for acoustic simulation (e.g., [Kirsch and Ewert, 2024b](#); [Mannall et al., 2024](#); [Tsingos et al., 2001](#)). The term scattering is typically used to describe wave-based effects on the sound field around a rigid object including the “illuminated” region and is used interchangeably with diffraction in the shadowed region.

Sound propagation can be modelled via two techniques: geometrical acoustics (GA) and wave-based methods. GA simplifies sound waves as sound rays and is computationally much more efficient than wave-based methods. Many modern room acoustics simulators use GA, such as the image-source method ([Allen and Berkley, 1979](#); [Savioja et al., 1999](#); [Schissler et al., 2014](#); [Schröder and Vorlaender,](#)

[2011](#)), ray tracing (e.g., [Krokstad et al., 1968](#)), and beam tracing (e.g., [Calamia and Svensson, 2006](#)). The major limitation of GA is that it is only strictly applicable when the size of geometrical structures and objects is larger than the wavelength. Accurate modeling of large wavelengths or small-scale objects necessitates wave-based methods, whose computational complexity increases dramatically with frequency. In interactive rendering, omitting wave-based diffraction effects in GA can lead to sound sources being abruptly silenced when transitioning into the shadowed region behind an obstacle, resulting in audible artifacts and reduced perceived plausibility of the scene (e.g., [Schissler et al., 2021](#)). To account for edge diffraction in the context of GA, several models have been proposed, for example, the Biot–Tolstoy–Medwin (BTM, [Biot and Tolstoy, 1957](#); [Medwin, 1981](#)) method, extensions thereof using secondary sources (BTMS, [Svensson et al., 1999](#)), as well as high-frequency asymptotic methods by [Pierce \(1974\)](#) and the Uniform Theory of Diffraction (UTD, [Kouyoumjian and Pathak, 1974](#)). Dramatically reducing computational complexity of these methods, a low-order filter representation for modelling first-order edge diffraction for infinite and finite edges has been proposed ([Ewert, 2022](#); [Kirsch and Ewert, 2023, 2024a,b](#)). This filter representation is suited for simulating edge diffraction of single edges, three-sided barriers, and objects composed of multiple edges such as plates or door frames with high precision and real-time capability.

To model scattering from rounded objects that are not well represented by a limited number of edges, a rigid sphere can serve as an abstract geometrical approximation.

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When modelling sphere scattering with either the receiver or source located on the sphere, such as in head-related transfer function (HRTF) or source directivity modelling, plane wave (far field) incidence has often been considered. For HRTF modelling, regarding the rigid sphere as the simplified spherical human head, [Brown and Duda \(1998\)](#) proposed a low-order (single-pole, single-zero) filter model to roughly reproduce the frequency response of the spherical head for plane wave incidence. This simple filter structure has been later extended by [Ewert *et al.* \(2021\)](#) with better control over the directional response, enabling representation for more complex source and receiver directivity modelling. Another filter model for the rigid sphere HRTF ([Spagnol *et al.*, 2012](#)) incorporates the dependence on source distance by distance-dependent filter parameters derived through curve fitting. This approach captures the variation in low-frequency magnitude with distance, a predominant characteristic of near-field HRTFs.

To model scenarios with a spherical object in the sound field and neither receiver nor source at the sphere's surface, some approaches exist. [Wirler *et al.* \(2021\)](#) developed parametric scattering filters to model the scattering of plane waves for general receiver positions, using neural networks for estimating the filter parameters. Earlier work by [Sun *et al.* \(1991\)](#) introduced a time-domain method that integrates the so-called "modal method" and the "physical optic method" ([Rubinow and Wu, 1956](#)), calculating the impulse response explicitly for backscattering (when the source and the receiver are co-located) of the rigid sphere. However, the transition frequency at which the two parts of the model are combined is relatively high, and the method is quite mathematically involved, limiting its practicality for virtual acoustics or applications demanding a low computational load.

Backscattering of electromagnetic waves from conducting spheres has been studied by [Rheinstein \(1968\)](#). He hypothesized that the characteristic rippled behavior observed in the frequency response arises from the interference between a specular reflection component at the front of the sphere and a creeping wave component traveling around the back side. This concept is directly related to the earlier work by [Franz and Deppermann \(1952\)](#) on backscattering from rigid cylinders. Modelling scattering from cylinders is also of interest for virtual acoustics applications, such as the simulation of pillars in architectural acoustics and forest reverberation ([Kaneko and Gamper, 2021](#); [Spratt and Abel, 2008](#)), where tree trunks can be represented by cylinders. [Spratt and Abel \(2008\)](#) approximated the time domain response of a rigid cylinder for plane wave incidence by two arrivals separated by a delay corresponding to the time difference for travelling around opposite sides of the cylinder.

Although the above-mentioned studies cover a wide range of solutions and applications related to modelling of rigid sphere scattering, most are limited to the far-field response with either receiver or source located on the sphere. Moreover, the filter models usually involve parameters empirically derived without physical foundation. Furthermore, because of the fundamentally different wave

behavior at low and high frequencies, most of these approaches fail to provide a good approximation in the high-frequency range, with exception of the mathematically rather involved method of [Sun *et al.* \(1991\)](#), where the low- and high-frequency ranges are modelled individually. Therefore, the development of a simplified and computationally efficient model for rigid sphere scattering, applicable to arbitrary source and receiver positions, is highly desirable.

In this work, we propose a combined low- and high-frequency method to model acoustic scattering of a rigid sphere with low-order filters, suited to be implemented with recursive digital filters for interactive real-time rendering. The proposed filter approximation has a physical basis and is generally applicable for arbitrary source and receiver distances. Our low-frequency approximation is based on modelling a small number of low-order spherical harmonic (SH) terms of the underlying analytical solution. The high-frequency approximation is based on GA assumptions and simplifies diffraction at the sphere to two discrete propagation paths, which are each modeled using concepts of edge diffraction and their filter representation. In combination, we obtain an efficient, physics-based filter model for the scattering of a rigid sphere. Results are analyzed in both frequency and time domain.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II describes the underlying theory and basic properties of rigid sphere scattering. Sections III and IV present the filter models for the low- and high-frequency range, respectively. The combined model and an analysis of errors in both frequency and time domain is provided in Sec. V. Discussion and conclusions are given in Secs. VI and VII.

II. RIGID SPHERE SCATTERING

Following [Beranek and Mellow \(2019\)](#), the analytical expression for the incident pressure field because of a point source is

$$p_i(k; r_1) = \frac{ik\rho_0c\tilde{U}_0e^{-ikr_1}}{4\pi r_1}, \quad (1)$$

where ρ_0 is the density of air, c is the speed of sound, k is the wave number, \tilde{U}_0 is the complex volume velocity at the source, and r_1 is the source-receiver distance. The corresponding diffracted pressure field of a rigid sphere is

$$p_s(k; a, d_r, d_s, \theta) = -\frac{k^2\rho_0c\tilde{U}_0}{4\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (2n+1) \cdot h_n^{(2)}(kd_r) \times \frac{j_n'(ka)}{h_n^{(2)}(ka)} h_n^{(2)}(kd_s) P_n(\cos\theta), \quad (2)$$

where a is the sphere radius, d_s and d_r are the distances from the sphere center to the source and receiver respectively, which are related to the source-receiver distance r_1 by $r_1 = \sqrt{d_s^2 + d_r^2 - 2d_r d_s \cos\theta}$. θ is the angle between the source and the receiver. $h_n^{(2)}(\cdot)$ is the spherical Hankel function of the second kind, $j_n(\cdot)$ is the spherical Bessel function,

and $P_n(\cdot)$ is the Legendre polynomial expressing the directivity of the SH terms.¹ The total sound pressure at the receiver position consists of the diffracted pressure and the incident pressure, i.e.,

$$p_t = p_s + p_i. \tag{3}$$

We can now normalize the scattered sound field of the rigid sphere by the source strength, maintaining distance-dependent delay and attenuation as

$$H_s(k; a, d_r, d_s, \theta) = p_s(k; a, d_r, d_s, \theta) \cdot \frac{4\pi}{ik\rho_0 c \tilde{U}_0} \\ = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (2n+1) \cdot ik \cdot h_n^{(2)}(kd_r) \\ \times \frac{j'_n(ka)}{h_n^{(2)}(ka)} h_n^{(2)}(kd_s) P_n(\cos \theta). \tag{4}$$

Note that in the context of HRTFs (e.g., Brown and Duda, 1998; Spagnol *et al.*, 2012), the transfer function takes a similar form; however, it is typically computed as the ratio between the total pressure at the sphere surface and the free-field incident pressure at the center of the sphere. In this work, we adopt the form of Eq. (4) to focus on the investigation of the diffracted field.

Figure 1(a) shows the magnitude responses of H_s [Eq. (4)], computing up to order $n_{max} = 50$ (solid lines) with a frequency resolution of 10 Hz for varying source and receiver distances, as indicated in the top left corner of the panels, and varying angles θ between source and receiver as indicated at the differently colored lines. Numbers with a gray background indicate geometrical conditions where the receiver is in the GA shadow zone of the sphere ($\theta > \arccos(d_r/a) + \arccos(d_s/a)$). A sphere radius of $a = 8.75$ cm, as commonly used in virtual acoustics to represent the average radius of the human head, results in the frequency axis provided at the bottom. The speed of sound was assumed as $c = 344$ m/s. For interpretation of the results with arbitrary sphere radius, the top x axis of Fig. 1(a) provides the normalized frequency range in units of ka . The magnitude responses of H_s generally show a high-shelving characteristic. The high frequencies are characterized by ripples, whose strength attenuates with increasing frequency and decreasing θ . Faint colors show the magnitude responses of the total field.

In Fig. 1(b), the corresponding impulse responses are shown, computed as the inverse Fourier transform of the frequency responses with a sampling rate $f_s = 72$ kHz. A Hanning window was applied in the frequency domain to obtain smooth results. The window function was defined by $H_w = 0.5 + 0.5\cos((f/f_{max})\pi)$, with $f_{max} = f_s/2$. The sampling rate, frequency resolution, and frequency-domain window function noted above apply throughout this study unless indicated otherwise. In the time domain, two dominant arrivals are visible, most prominently for θ of 180° (red) and 120° (yellow). When the receiver is illuminated (θ without gray text background), the impulse response starts with a peaked

FIG. 1. (a) Magnitude responses for the transfer function of the diffracted (solid color, obtained from Eq. (4)) and total (faint color) field of the rigid sphere. The panels show different source and receiver distance combinations, with the gray text background indicating geometrical conditions where the sphere occludes the receiver from the direct sound. (b) Impulse responses corresponding to (a), with amplitude normalized to the maximum amplitude at 0° and the corresponding distance of each panel. The time unit is defined relative to the radius as $2a/c$. An offset is applied between the impulse responses of different angles for better visibility. Dashed vertical lines in the upper panel of (b) indicate the time of the second arrival. An example (black lines) for the separation of the two arrivals for the case $d_s = 10a$, $d_r = 2a$, $\theta = 120^\circ$ (yellow) is shown in the two bottom panels. The black dashed line corresponds to the first arrival, and the black dotted line corresponds to the second arrival. Considering temporal windowing applied for the separation, the frequency responses are only shown above 312 Hz. The frequency response of the first arrival is only valid above that limit, and that of the second arrival might be affected by low-frequency components of the first arrival below that limit.

arrival, followed by a weaker and more temporally spread second arrival. When the receiver is shadowed, the first arrival starts with a negative peak. The relative strength of the second arrival increases with θ . The time delay between the first and the second arrival decreases with θ .

To better understand the behavior of the two arrivals, for the example case at $d_s = 10a$, $d_r = 2a$, $\theta = 120^\circ$ (yellow, in the bottom panels), the two arrivals in the impulse response were temporally separated at time point $6.32a/c$ (corresponding to 3.205 ms) as indicated with the black dashed and dotted lines. Disregarding the low-frequency range (< 312 Hz), which is affected by time windowing (rectangular window with 0.139 ms Hanning ramps at both ends), the first arrival has a fractional-order high-pass behavior (approximately 1.5 dB/octave) as visible in the bottom left panel. The second arrival has a low-pass behavior with an approximate slope of -6 dB/octave.

The analysis above highlights two fundamental characteristics for rigid sphere scattering: (i) the scattered field generally exhibits a high-shelving spectral characteristic, and (ii) the scattered field is the result of the interference of two dominant arrivals in the time domain, each characterized by a simple low-pass or high-pass behavior. The method proposed in this work aims to model the scattered field of the rigid sphere by reproducing these two fundamental characteristics, corresponding to the low-frequency and high-frequency approximation. The low-frequency approximation models the high-shelving characteristic by multiple low-order high-pass or high-shelving filters, and the high-frequency approximation models the two arrivals by two diffraction paths under GA assumptions.

III. LOW-FREQUENCY FILTER APPROXIMATION

According to the characteristics of the spherical Bessel and Hankel functions $j_n(\cdot)$ and $h_n^{(2)}(\cdot)$, the low-frequency behavior of the diffracted field is dominated by the low-order terms in the summation in Eq. (4). We therefore propose to model the low-frequency behavior with only a small number of these terms, reflecting a wave-based approximation. Reciprocity of the problem suggests two structurally identical terms for the dependence on source and receiver distances. Dependence on θ is described individually by the “directivity function” $P_n(\cos \theta)$.

A. Filter structure

We reformulate Eq. (4) using two structurally identical terms expressing the d_s and d_r dependence, respectively,

$$H_s(k; a, d_r, d_s, \theta) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (2n + 1) \cdot P_n(\cos \theta) \cdot \prod_{d_{r,s}} \sqrt{ik \cdot \frac{j'_n(ka)}{h_n^{(2)}(ka)}} h_n^{(2)}(kd_{r,s}). \quad (5)$$

Comparing to Eq. (4), the $ik \cdot (j'_n(ka)/h_n^{(2)}(ka))$ factor is split up in Eq. (5) into two factors by a square root to obtain symmetric formulations only differing by the d_s or d_r argument. As the role of both terms is exactly the same, we will uniformly refer to either distance term using d , omitting the subscripts in the following. The advantage of this approach in comparison to modelling the combined shelving filter characteristic (see Fig. 1), is that the problem simplifies to a parameterized gain and cutoff frequency only related to the sphere radius and a single (source or receiver) distance. Based on these parameters, the slope of the overall shelving characteristic for the diffracted field, which depends on both distances, can be constructed by low-order filters with uniform structure, as will be shown next. The solid lines in Fig. 2 show the frequency spectra for the d -dependent term from the 0th order ($n = 0$) to the 3rd order ($n = 3$) for different distances from the sphere (see Fig. 2 panels). As $j_n(\cdot)$ and $h_n^{(2)}(\cdot)$ inherently contain distance-related attenuation, the overall energy of each term decreases with d . Neglecting the comb-filter

FIG. 2. Magnitude (left column) and phase (right column) responses of the d -dependent term as in Eq. (5) (solid lines; anal., analytical) from the 0th order to the 3rd order and the corresponding filter representation (dashed lines). The linear phase $k((a/2) - d)$ corresponding to the travelling time of the diffracted component is removed when plotting the phase responses. It can be noted the square root expression in Eq. (5) halves the phase, resulting in $\pi/2$ phase jumps at the zero crossings of the transfer functions.

characteristics at high frequencies starting from about $ka = 1.6$, the terms consistently show a high-pass (0th order) or high-shelving (1st to 3rd order) characteristic (Fig. 2, left column), which indicates the possibility to approximate each individual term up to a certain frequency with a simple filter. Figure 2 illustrates that the slope of the high-pass or high-shelving characteristic in the magnitude responses depends on the order n , whereas the direct current (DC) gain (the low-frequency “plateau”) depends on both d and n . Except for 0th order, the low frequency energy decreases as n increases, with the rate of reduction varying with d . For example, for $d = 1a$, the difference in DC gain between the 1st and 3rd order is less than 2 dB, whereas for $d = 10a$, this difference is more than 40 dB. It is also obvious that for $d = 1a$ [Fig. 2(a)], the frequency response is basically flat for $ka < 1.6$ and $n > 0$, and the shelving behaviour only manifests for larger distances.

The suggested model structure for the low-frequency approximation using a low-order filter representation is illustrated in Fig. 3. It is indicated in Fig. 3 that the critical parameters (gains and cutoff frequencies) for the frequency response of the filters to be defined depend on both distance d and radius a , ensuring the generality of the filter model. Below, the frequency-domain characteristics of the d -dependent terms are analyzed, and principles for determining the filter parameters are presented. Unless otherwise

FIG. 3. Model structure for the low-frequency approximation with filter representation for the 0th-, 1st-, and 2nd-order terms of the analytical solution. Each pathway represents an individual order. The first two columns represent the filters depending on source and receiver distances, respectively. The all-pass filters applied for correcting the phase mismatch for the 0th- and 2nd-order terms are also shown. The output is the weighted summation of the filter representation for different orders. The lower part in the dashed box is the additional low-pass filter representation to account for the DC gain of the 3rd-order term, which can be applied optionally depending on the required accuracy. HP, high-pass; HS, high-shelving; LP, low-pass; AP, all-pass.

stated, all filters mentioned in this section are single or cascaded first-order low- or high-pass (Butterworth) filters.

1. 0th order

For the 0th order, the magnitude spectrum for the d -dependent term shows a high-pass characteristic with a 6 dB/octave slope. The key parameters are the cutoff frequency $f_0(a)$ and the high-frequency gain $G_{0,\infty}(a, d)$. The d -dependent term can then be approximated by a first-order high-pass filter (see dashed lines in Fig. 2), with empirically fitted parameters $f_0(a) = 3c/5\pi a$ and $G_{0,\infty}(a, d) = \sqrt{a}/\sqrt{2d}$.

The phase relationship of the 0th-order term can be analytically derived as a function of a and d as

$$\phi_0(k; d, a) = \frac{5}{4}\pi + k\left(\frac{a}{2} - d\right) + \frac{1}{2}\arctan\left(\frac{1}{ka}\right). \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) indicates that the phase response of the 0th-order term tends toward $-(1/2)\pi$ as the frequency approaches 0 (DC), and contains a distance-dependent delay (linear phase) component $k((a/2) - d)$, plus a non-linear component depending only on ka . The linear-phase component in this study is implemented as a fractional delay in the frequency domain, avoiding phase errors. A corresponding time-domain implementation would require the use of fractional-delay filters, such as truncated sinc interpolation (Oppenheim *et al.*, 1999) or Thiran infinite impulse response (IIR) all-pass filters (Thiran, 1971). The non-linear component is partly replicated by the low-order filters (Fig. 2, right column), whereas the remaining phase difference hints to additional delays from higher-order diffraction and remains a source of approximation error. The directivity of the 0th-order term is uniform with a value of 1.

2. Higher orders

For the 1st order, the magnitude spectrum for the d -dependent term shows a high-shelving characteristic with

a 6 dB/octave slope. This can be approximated by adding up a 1st-order low-pass filter and a 1st-order high-pass filter, resulting in a 1st-order high-shelving filter. The key parameters are the cutoff frequency $f_1(a)$, the DC gain $G_{1,DC}(a, d)$, and the high-frequency gain $G_{1,\infty}(a, d)$. $G_{1,DC}(a, d)$ was derived analytically and has the following form:

$$G_{1,DC}(a, d) = \frac{1}{d^2} \sqrt{\frac{a^3}{6}}. \quad (7)$$

The empirically derived filter parameters are: $f_1(a) = 3c/5\pi a$, $G_{1,\infty}(a, d) = \sqrt{a}/2d$. The analytical phase for the 1st-order term is

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1(k; d, a) = & \frac{5}{4}\pi + k\left(\frac{a}{2} - d\right) - \arctan\left(\frac{1}{kd}\right) \\ & - \frac{1}{2}\arctan\left(\frac{k^2a^2 - 2}{2ka}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The Appendix presents the derivation of the analytical DC gain and phase response for the 1st-order term, as well as principles for deriving the corresponding expressions for other orders. The directivity of the 1st-order term has a figure-of-eight pattern.

Similarly, the 2nd-order term can be approximated by a high-shelving filter with a 12-dB/octave slope, which is constructed by cascading two 1st-order high-shelving filters. The analytical DC gain and phase relationship for the 2nd-order term are

$$G_{2,DC}(a, d) = \frac{1}{d^3} \sqrt{\frac{2a^5}{15}}, \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_2(k; d, a) = & \frac{5}{4}\pi + k\left(\frac{a}{2} - d\right) - \arctan\left(\frac{3kd}{k^2d^2 - 3}\right) \\ & + \frac{1}{2}\arctan\left(\frac{4k^2a^2 - 9}{k^3a^3 - 9ka}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

TABLE I. Summary of the filter type and parameters for the low-frequency approximation; parameters shown in bold are derived analytically, all others are obtained empirically.

	Filter type	Cutoff frequency	Gain(s)
$n = 0$	1st-order high-pass	$f_0(a) = \frac{3c}{5\pi a}$	$G_{0,\infty}(a, d) = \frac{\sqrt{a}}{\sqrt{2}d}$
$n = 1$	1st-order high-shelving	$f_1(a) = \frac{3c}{5\pi a}$	$G_{1,DC}(a, d) = \frac{1}{d^2} \sqrt{\frac{a^3}{6}}$, $G_{1,\infty}(a, d) = \frac{\sqrt{a}}{2d}$
$n = 2$	2nd-order high-shelving	$f_2(a) = \frac{c}{\pi a}$	$G_{2,DC}(a, d) = \frac{1}{d^3} \sqrt{\frac{2a^5}{15}}$, $G_{2,\infty}(a, d) = \frac{\sqrt{a}}{2d}$
$n = 3$	1st-order low-pass	$f_3(a) = f_2(a)$	$G_{3,DC}(a, d) = \frac{1}{d^4} \sqrt{\frac{3a^7}{28}}$

The empirically derived filter parameters are $f_2(a) = c/\pi a$, $G_{2,\infty}(a, d) = \sqrt{a}/2d$. An overview of the filter type and parameters for orders 0 to 3 is presented in Table I.

The 3rd-order term can be approximated by a high-shelving filter with an 18 dB/octave slope, with the following DC gain:

$$G_{3,DC}(a, d) = \frac{1}{d^4} \sqrt{\frac{3a^7}{28}}. \quad (11)$$

Analysis of Eqs. (6), (8) and (10) shows that regardless of order n , the linear phase component is determined by $((a/2) - d)$, and the DC phase for $n > 0$ has a constant value, π . All the higher-order terms have a unique non-linear phase component with d dependence.

The dashed lines in Fig. 2 show the magnitude and phase responses of the filter representation of the d -dependent term. The filters generally agree very well with the analytical term, except for some deviations, which can be observed in the transition regions of the high-shelving filters for the 2nd- and 3rd-order terms.

B. Results

The filter structure introduced above can also be extended to approximate higher-order terms in Eq. (5) using higher-order filters. Because the low-frequency energy of $j_n(\cdot)$ and $h_n^{(2)}(\cdot)$ decreases rapidly with increasing order (Wiscombe, 1980; Kennedy *et al.*, 2007), and terms of order $n > ka$ have very little contribution to the overall energy of the sound field, it is expected that a good low-frequency approximation of the full analytical solution can be achieved with a small number of terms, with the truncation order chosen to balance accuracy and efficiency. It should also be noted that because the diffracted field is a spatially smooth function resulting from the contributions of an infinite number of terms with order-dependent directivity patterns, adding a higher-order component may degrade the result at certain θ angles rather than improve it.

A filter model with the representation for only the 0th- and 1st-order terms would be ideal in terms of computational complexity. However, the zeros at 90° and 270° in the figure-of-eight directivity of the 1st-order term will result in a relatively large approximation error at

these angles, where only the representation for the 0th-order term takes an effect. Therefore, the filter representation for the first three terms (0th, 1st, and 2nd order) is used in our basic model structure (see Fig. 3). Figure 4 shows the magnitude and phase responses of the low-frequency filter representation (dashed, faint lines), combining both the d_r - and d_s -dependent terms. Results for different angles are shown in each panel, and different panels show the effect of different d_r , for a fixed distance $d_s = 2a$. The sum of the corresponding 0th- to 2nd-order analytical terms (dotted lines, hereafter referred to “order-truncated analytical solution”) and the analytical solution

FIG. 4. Magnitude (left column) and phase (right column) responses of the analytical solution for the diffracted field (solid lines; anal., analytical), the order-truncated analytical solution (dotted lines; trunc., truncated), the output of the basic filter model (dashed, faint lines), and the filter model output with phase and DC gain correction (dashed lines; corr., corrected). The gray text background indicates scenarios where the receiver is geometrically shadowed by the sphere.

(summation up to the 50th order, solid lines) are shown as reference. In the left column of Fig. 4, beside the exact match to the order-truncated analytical solution at DC, the filter approximation also correctly captures the shelving behavior at the low- to middle-frequency range. For ka between 0.16 and 1.6, frequency-dependent magnitude deviations between the filter approximation and the order-truncated analytical solution start to appear, the amount of which depends on θ : in Fig. 4(c), as ka approaches 1.6, a good match is still observed for 0° , whereas 120° shows a large deviation.

When comparing to the analytical solution, the representation with the first three terms reproduces the low-frequency magnitude well, except at small distances [see Fig. 4(a)], where a relatively large error in DC gain is caused by order truncation (shown by the differences between the dotted and the solid lines). This error can be related to Fig. 2, where at small distances the energy of the 3rd-order term is comparable to the lower-order terms and therefore still plays an important role in the summation.² For simulations that require smaller distances, higher-order filters can be added following the principles presented earlier in this section at the expense of computational efficiency. Alternatively, we propose to account for the DC gain of the 3rd-order term in addition to the filter model structure introduced above, utilizing the property that all the d -dependent terms as in Eq. (5) are in phase at DC (except for the 0th-order term). Therefore, an optional 1st-order low-pass filter with the DC gain for the 3rd-order term is added to the filter model (Fig. 3, lower part). This solution avoids using higher-order filters while reducing the approximation error at DC. Analytically derived DC gains for higher orders can be accumulated to further improve performance with a modest increase in computational cost for parameter calculations.

We have shown above that the non-linear phase relationship at low frequency can be reproduced by the low-order filters to some extent. However, the filter representation generally produces a smaller phase than the analytical term except for $n = 1$ (see Fig. 2, left column). This phase mismatch contributes to the magnitude deviation for ka between 0.16 and 1.6 as observed in Fig. 4. To compensate for that, a 1st-order all-pass filter with an empirically derived cutoff frequency, $f_{c,ap}(a) = c/a$, is applied to the 0th-order and 2nd-order filter representation.

Figure 4 also shows the magnitude and phase responses of the filter approximation with phase and DC gain corrections (dashed lines). The effect of the phase correction is most evident near $ka = 1.6$, where the corrected phase responses align more closely with the analytical solution (solid lines). The magnitude responses after correction closely match those of the analytical solution for $ka < 1.6$. The remaining DC gain deviation for $d_r = 1a$ [Fig. 4(a)] is attributed to the contribution of higher-order terms. It should be noted that the fractional-delay implementation of the propagation delay is important to ensure an exact

representation of the linear phase components (not shown in phase responses), avoiding additional errors.

IV. HIGH-FREQUENCY FILTER APPROXIMATION

In the scope of GA, diffraction by the sphere can be regarded as consisting of an infinite number of diffraction paths. The total field at the receiver position results from the interference of all paths plus the incident field. When the receiver is not shadowed by the sphere, some of the paths bounce back at the illuminated side of the sphere. Other paths travel around the back side of the sphere, “bend back,” and arrive at the receiver later in time. When the receiver is shadowed by the sphere, all paths travel around the sphere and bend toward the direction of the receiver.

As previously observed in Fig. 1(a), the scattered time domain response of the sphere consists of two predominant arrivals with a position-dependent time delay. Therefore, a simplistic GA diffraction model appears reasonable with representing only two paths. Furthermore, we assume that each diffraction path can be described using concepts from edge diffraction modelling. Thus, the following geometrical simplifications were made: (i) For path reduction, we take the cross section of the sphere with the source (S), the receiver (R), and the center (O). In this two-dimensional plane, the longest (typically bent around the sphere) and shortest (typically reflected off the sphere) sound propagation paths are taken as the two representative paths. The difference in travel distances determines their relative magnitude and time delay, which should correspond to those for the two arrivals illustrated in Fig. 1(b). (ii) We account for effects of diffraction in the two representative paths by using proxy edges. The position and properties of the proxy edges determine the frequency spectra for each path [see Fig. 1(a)].

A. Diffraction path model and “proxy edge” approximation

Figure 5 illustrates the two representative geometrical configurations, with the GA shadow zone indicated in light gray. The shadow zone is bounded by the geometrical shadow boundary of the sphere. When the receiver is illuminated [Fig. 5(a)], the specular reflection from the sphere is not modeled separately but included in the scattered field. In this case, the path on the illuminated side of the sphere is fundamentally different from the path on the shadowed side. The reflection path (corresponding to edge e_1) is constructed via the specular reflection point Z on the surface of the sphere. Given that there is no analytical solution for the so-called Alhazen–Ptolemy problem, the point has to be determined numerically, with fast approaches existing (Fujimura *et al.*, 2019; Kollas, 2017; Müller *et al.*, 2021). The longer path (corresponding to edge e_2) represents the bending in propagation direction. It is constructed with the “bending point” lying halfway between the tangent point of the receiver (RT₂) and the tangent point of the source (ST₂) on the shadowed surface of the sphere.

FIG. 5. Two-dimensional view for the two representative geometrical arrangements for the rigid sphere with the edge diffraction-based model. ST_1 , ST_2 , RT_1 , and RT_2 are the tangent points related to the source and the receiver for paths 1 and 2, respectively. (a) Receiver illuminated, (b) receiver shadowed. The knife edges are indicated in blue, with a dashed part suggesting that the edges extend to infinity (half plane). The edges also extend to infinity in the plane perpendicular to the depicted source-center-receiver plane. All apex points³ lie on the surface of the sphere. For the bending components, the source is always on the opposite side of the edge with respect to the receiver. Solid black lines with arrows denote the sound propagation paths of the edge diffraction model. Dashed black lines denote the paths for assumed sound ray propagation bending around the sphere. Arrows denote the direction of propagation. See text for more details.

To obtain a computationally efficient model for the two diffracted paths, we employ and modify the universal diffraction filter approximation (UDFA) introduced by Kirsch and Ewert (2023), which offers a fractional-order low-pass filter description with parametric roll-off control for edge diffraction that applies to arbitrary geometrical configurations using physics-based parameters. Depending on the geometry, a description of edge diffraction is possible with two to four diffraction terms. This framework can be extended using different underlying diffraction solutions, including UTD (Kouyoumjian and Pathak, 1974) and BTMS (Biot and Tolstoy, 1957; Medwin, 1981; Svensson et al., 1999). In this work, we implement the two-term filter approximation of “knife edges,” or half planes with a disappearing interior wedge angle, for the edge diffraction model. Given that the geometry of the sphere (especially considering the surface curvature) differs fundamentally from that of any wedge, the required modifications to the diffraction filters would always be substantial even when larger interior wedge angles were used. The key idea is therefore to employ the concept of a proxy edge rather than adhering strictly to the physical geometry. The knife edge (with only two diffraction terms) appears to be particularly suited as a base for the modified proxy edge. A further general advantage of applying the edge diffraction filter approximation here is that it inherently covers the principle of reciprocity.

The corresponding proxy edge configuration is as follows: An infinite knife edge e_1 (half plane) is placed at Z with its edge plane tangent to the sphere (indicated in blue in Fig. 5). Edge e_2 is placed at the corresponding bending point at the shadowed surface of the sphere, and the edge plane passes through the source. Both edges extend to infinity, disregarding the fact that the diameter of the sphere is finite and that the surface is curved.

When the receiver is shadowed [see Fig. 5(b)], both paths are constructed *via* the bending point at halfway of the arc between the tangent points (RT_1 and ST_1 , RT_2 and ST_2).

In this case, both proxy edges are configured as for e_2 in the illuminated case with the source located in the edge plane. For a receiver in the illuminated zone in the upper hemisphere ($\theta \leq 180^\circ$), as θ increases, the location of edge e_1 gradually approaches ST_1 . When the receiver there reaches the geometrical shadow boundary of the sphere, the apex of e_1 coincides with ST_1 , and the edge plane of e_1 passes through the source. Continuing into the shadow zone, the source stays in the edge plane. Once θ exceeds 180° , the positions of e_1 and e_2 are exchanged, with e_1 consistently representing the shorter path and e_2 the longer path.

For each edge, the corresponding filter representation is composed of two terms that represent the diffracted reflected and diffracted incident component, respectively (Ewert, 2022). The terms are expressed as fractional-order low-pass filters whose cutoff frequency and gain are directly related to the source and receiver positions. Depending on the bending (deflection) angle, each term either has a positive or negative sign. A detailed description of the general behavior of the terms for the edge diffraction filters is given by Ewert (2022). The proxy edge configuration described above involves three different geometrical arrangements, with the following behavior in the diffraction terms: (i) When illuminated, the receiver lies on the reflection boundary of edge e_1 . In this case, the transfer function of the diffracted reflected term is spectrally flat, with unit gain and an infinite cutoff frequency. (ii) When the receiver is located at the shadow boundary of the sphere, the source lies on the edge plane of edge e_1 , resulting in a co-planar reflection and shadow boundary of the edge.⁴ Therefore, the diffracted reflected and diffracted incident terms are identical, both exhibiting a flat frequency response. (iii) When the receiver is shadowed by the sphere, with the source still on the edge plane of e_1 , the reflection and shadow boundaries are still co-planar. Accordingly, the diffracted reflected and diffracted incident terms remain identical, but their transfer function exhibits a low-pass characteristic.

Overall, with this proxy edge design, in principle, only a single filter needs to be computed in each scenario as described above, and the geometrical continuity of the edge diffraction model is ensured across the shadow boundary of the sphere.

The behavior of the diffraction terms for edge e_2 is similar to that of the third case for edge e_1 described above. The propagation paths bending around the sphere (Fig. 5, dashed black lines) are used to determine the distance-dependent attenuation and time delay of the edge diffraction filters. For example, the total length of $(RT_2-S + \text{arc}(RT_1-RT_2) + R-RT_2)$ in Fig. 5(b) is taken as the length for path 2. In this study, the linear phase component associated with the propagation delay of the two paths is implemented as fractional delays in the frequency domain.

B. Modifications to the proxy edge approximation

Investigation into the behavior of the edge diffraction filters and the physical differences between the assumed proxy infinite knife edges and the real geometry of the sphere reveals the following: (i) The fractional-order edge diffraction filter cannot accurately represent the -6 dB/octave slope for the low-pass behavior of the second arrival as shown in Fig. 1(a). (ii) The distance-related magnitude attenuation rate for the infinite edge diffraction model is different from that for the sphere. One can imagine that when both source and receiver distances are much larger than the sphere radius, the sphere effectively acts as a secondary source of the diffracted sound. In contrast, the knife edge, modeled as an infinite half plane, never becomes such an apparent point source, regardless of distance. (iii) In the illuminated zone, as the receiver approaches the sphere, the distance to the apex point of edge e_1 decreases. When this distance becomes sufficiently small, the knife edge effectively becomes “invisible,” resulting in a significant reduction in the magnitude of the diffracted field, whereas the sphere surface becomes effectively “larger.” A similar magnitude reduction occurs when the receiver is positioned near the shadow boundary of the edge, regardless of whether it is in the illuminated or shadowed zone.

To deal with these limitations of the proxy knife edge simplification, we apply the following modifications, which result in a modified edge diffraction model.

1. 1st-order filter modification

The edge diffraction filter corresponding to edge e_2 is replaced with a 1st-order (Butterworth) low-pass filter with an empirically modified gain and cutoff frequency related to that of the edge diffraction filter,

$$f_{c,e_2mod} = 20f_{c,e_2}, \tag{12a}$$

$$G_{e_2mod} = 0.25G_{e_2}. \tag{12b}$$

In Fig. 6, an example where the modified edge diffraction filters resemble the two arrivals in the analytical solution, i.e., the fractional high-pass behavior of the 1st arrival and the 1st-order low-pass behavior of the 2nd arrival at $ka > 1.6$, is shown. The desired -6 dB/octave slope of the

FIG. 6. Magnitude responses for the two arrivals (arr.) from the proxy edge diffraction model, in contrast to those of the analytical (anal.) solution. The geometrical condition is the same as in Fig. 1(c), with $d_s = 10a$, $d_r = 2a$, $\theta = 120^\circ$.

2nd arrival would also have been obtained using diffraction on two consecutive edges (e.g., a three-sided barrier) to better approximate the path bending around the sphere.

2. Distance attenuation modification

In the illuminated zone, an empirically obtained gain correction factor g is applied to the filter corresponding to edge e_1 as follows:

$$g = \frac{1}{d_r d_s} \cdot \left(\frac{a^2}{4\pi^2 d_r d_s} + \frac{a}{\pi^2} \right) \left(\left(\frac{a}{d_r d_s} + 1 \right) (\cos \theta - 1) + 2\pi \right). \tag{13}$$

In contrast to the infinite edge where the total path length determines the magnitude attenuation, the finite sphere in principle causes a $1/d_r d_s$ attenuation rate. Further modifications [components in the brackets in Eq. (13)] were empirically fitted based on the magnitude differences of proxy edge and sphere scattering.

3. Small-distance modification

To account for applications where distances are small, we apply another modification for the illuminated zone. The modification is based on the observation that the distance-dependent variation in the diffracted field is much less compared to the angle-dependent variation (see also Spagnol et al., 2012). For the same θ , the spectral characteristics of the magnitude response for the analytical diffracted field only shows a small amount of change as the receiver (or source) distance decrease from $2a$ to a . Below, we denote the distances in a slightly different way, revealing the reciprocity, as $d_> = \max(d_r, d_s)$, $d_< = \min(d_r, d_s)$. For scenarios where $d_< < 2a$, the diffraction filter for edge e_1 is replaced by a scaled version of the corresponding filter for $d_< = 2a$, i.e.,

$$H_1(d_>, d_<, \theta) \leftarrow g_c H_1(d_>, 2a, \theta), \tag{14}$$

TABLE II. Summary of the modifications applied to the proxy edge diffraction model.

Edge associated	Description	Parameters/formula	Geometrical condition(s)
e ₁	Apply an empirically obtained gain correction factor g	$g = \frac{1}{d_r d_s} \cdot \left(\frac{a^2}{4\pi^2 d_r d_s} + \frac{a}{\pi^2} \right) \left(\left(\frac{a}{d_r \cdot d_s} + 1 \right) (\cos \theta - 1) + 2\pi \right)$	Illuminated zone
e ₁	Replace the diffraction filter with a scaled version of the corresponding filter for $d_{<} = 2a$	$g_c = \left(\frac{2a}{d_{>}} + 1 \right) \cdot \cos \theta \cdot e^{(2a/d_{<})^{-1}} + 1$ ($d_{>} = \max(d_r, d_s)$, $d_{<} = \min(d_r, d_s)$).	$d_{<} < 2a$ in illuminated zone
e ₁	Apply an upper limit to the cutoff frequency of the diffracted incident term	$f_{c1,e1} = \min(f_{c1,e1}, f_{c,upper})$, $f_{c,upper} = 8$ kHz.	All
e ₁	Redefine shadow boundary, at which the sign of the edge diffraction filter is reversed	$\theta'_{SB} = \theta_{SB} + \Delta\theta_{SB}$, $\Delta\theta_{SB} = \begin{cases} 100^\circ \left(\frac{a}{d_{r,s}} - 0.5 \right)^2 - 14^\circ, & d_{r,s} < 2a, \\ -14^\circ, & d_{r,s} \geq 2a. \end{cases}$	All
e ₂	Replace the fractional-order edge diffraction filter with a 1st-order low-pass filter	$f_{c,e2mod} = 20f_{c,e2}$, $G_{e2mod} = 0.25G_{e2}$.	All

where the scaling factor g_c is empirically defined as

$$g_c = \left(\frac{2a}{d_{>}} + 1 \right) \cdot \cos \theta \cdot e^{(2a/d_{<})^{-1}} + 1. \tag{15}$$

This scaling factor provides an approximation for the variation of the high-frequency gain with distance.

Two further modifications were introduced to better match the behavior of the proxy edge approximation with that of the rigid sphere in the transitional region (near the geometrical shadow boundary). First, an upper limit, $f_{c,upper} = 8$ kHz (or generally $2c/a$), is applied to the cutoff frequency of the diffracted incident term to correct for the magnitude reduction in the transitional region. Note that with this limitation, the otherwise identical cutoff frequencies of the diffracted incident and reflected terms in the shadow zone (given that the source is always in the edge plane), are different, and two filters are required instead of a single filter. Second, variation of the analytical solution in time domain exhibits a typical sign reversal of the first peak in the impulse response near the geometrical shadow boundary of the sphere, but not precisely at it. In contrast, the proxy edge model consistently produces a sign reversal in the edge diffraction filter for edge e_1 at the geometrical shadow boundary. To address this discrepancy and to improve the approximation accuracy, we introduce a “redefined shadow boundary” for the sphere, at which the sign of the diffraction filter for edge e_1 is reversed. Based on analysis of the impulse responses of the analytical solution, we determine a distance-dependent correction angle $\Delta\theta_{SB}$, which adjusts the geometrical shadow boundary θ_{SB} to obtain the redefined shadow boundary θ'_{SB} of the sphere,

$$\theta'_{SB} = \theta_{SB} + \Delta\theta_{SB}, \tag{16}$$

with

$$\Delta\theta_{SB} = \begin{cases} 100^\circ \left((a/d_{<}) - 0.5 \right)^2 - 14^\circ, & d_{<} < 2a, \\ -14^\circ, & d_{<} \geq 2a. \end{cases} \tag{17}$$

This adjustment better aligns the model with the observed impulse response of the analytical solution.

Table II summarizes the above-mentioned modifications to the basic edge diffraction filter model, grouped according to their associated edge. The overall model structure for the high-frequency approximation is shown in Fig. 7.

C. Results

Figure 8 shows the magnitude and phase responses for the modified edge diffraction filter representation (dashed lines) in the same format as in Fig. 4, now focusing on the high-frequency range for $ka > 1.6$. Except for the small-distance case in Fig. 8(a), the model generally captures the high-frequency gain variation. The large magnitude offset (about 6 dB) for 60° in Fig. 8(a) indicates that the scaling factor g_c provides only a rough fit to the gain variation for the corresponding case. However, analysis of the overall quality of fit for different distance combinations reveals that g_c is a good solution for larger $d_{>}$. Therefore, g_c could possibly be modified for applications where both $d_{>}$ and $d_{<}$ are small. The right column of Fig. 8 illustrates that at high frequencies, the filter model successfully replicates the overall phase response.

FIG. 7. Model structure for high-frequency approximation with the edge diffraction filter representation adapted from UDFA. The upper two (fractional-order) low-pass (LP) filters correspond to the shorter path (associated with e_1), and represent the diffracted incident and reflected term, respectively. The lower first-order low-pass filter corresponds to the longer path (associated with e_2).

FIG. 8. Magnitude (left column) and phase (right column) responses for the suggested high-frequency approximation (dashed lines), in contrast to the analytical solution (anal., solid lines). Grey text background indicates scenarios where the receiver is geometrically shadowed by the sphere.

In the middle- and high-frequency range, the model successfully captures the fundamental ripple characteristics of the sphere’s response, regardless of whether the receiver is shadowed or not. This demonstrates the effectiveness of the representation by two diffraction paths and the proxy edge model. Slight discrepancies in the ripple positions indicate that although the relative magnitude and delay for the two defined diffraction paths closely approximate those of the actual arrivals, they do not align exactly. For $\theta = 180^\circ$, the analytical magnitude response exhibits significantly larger ripple amplitudes compared to the approximation. This discrepancy is primarily attributed to the “bright spot” effect at 180° , which results from the constructive interference of an infinite number of identical paths for the real sphere. This effect that cannot be fully reproduced by the suggested two-path diffraction model.

V. COMBINED LOW- AND HIGH-FREQUENCY FILTER REPRESENTATION

A. Magnitude and phase blending

To be able to depict and analyze the errors of the suggested model in the entire frequency range, we combine the low- and high-frequency approximation using magnitude and phase blending. To achieve a smooth transition, we apply a simple sigmoid function,

$$w(f) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{(f-f_i)/100}}, \quad (18)$$

where f_i is the transition frequency (set to 1 kHz in this study). The slope parameter 1/100 was chosen empirically to achieve a smooth 400 Hz transition around f_i . Within this range, the low- and high-frequency approximations remain close to the analytical solution without abrupt deviations, ensuring perceptually continuous blending. The blended frequency response can be expressed as

$$H_{appr} = (w \cdot M_{appr,lf} + (1 - w) \cdot M_{appr,hf}) \times e^{-i(w \cdot \phi_{appr,lf} + (1-w) \cdot \phi_{appr,hf})}, \quad (19)$$

where $M_{appr,lf}$ and $M_{appr,hf}$ represent the magnitude for the low- and high-frequency approximations, respectively, and $\phi_{appr,lf}$ and $\phi_{appr,hf}$ are their corresponding phase. This formulation ensures that the magnitude and phase are blended separately. The blending method applied here is primarily for evaluation purposes rather than practical implementation.

A comprehensive overview of the magnitude responses of the combined model approximation is presented in Figs. 9(a)–9(f) for various distances d_s and d_r and angles θ , covering the scenario for binaural rendering or source directivity with either receiver or source on the sphere (here $d_s = 1a$), and for more general object scattering with both source and receiver at a certain distance from the sphere ($d_s, d_r > 1a$). The solid lines represent the analytical solution, whereas the dashed lines represent the approximation. The blended frequency responses generally fit with the analytical solution, although some deviations occur near the transition frequency because of the deviations of the low- and high- frequency approximation before blending (see Figs. 4 and 8). Figures 9(a)–9(f) further demonstrate that with the high-frequency gain correction applied, the filter model output closely matches the analytical solution across various distances.

Figure 9(g) shows the impulse responses at different angles for the case $d_s = 2a, d_r = 4a$, in contrast to the analytical solution. For $0^\circ, 60^\circ$, and 120° , the first peak is well reproduced by our model, whereas the second peak exhibits a slightly larger delay than the analytical solution, corresponding to the shifted ripples in Fig. 9(b). This discrepancy may arise because the geometrically constructed path length bending around the sphere (Fig. 5, dashed black lines) represents the shortest path only in the high-frequency limit ($ka \gg 1$), whereas the true propagation path length is frequency dependent. For 180° , the second peak from the approximation is considerably weaker than the analytical solution, corresponding to the smaller ripples in Fig. 9(b). This reduced second peak also causes the larger deviations near the transition frequency at large distances, as shown in Figs. 9(d) and 9(f).

Figure 9(h) shows the output of our model for a far-field HRTF modelling scenario, compared with the analytical solution and the simple spherical head filter model by Brown and Duda (1998, dotted lines). Responses are calculated for the case $d_s = 1a, d_r = 20a$. As can be observed,

FIG. 9. (a)–(f) Magnitude responses of the diffracted field for the blended model output (dashed lines) for different geometrical configurations, in comparison to the analytical solution (solid lines). d_s varies from $1a$ to $10a$, whereas d_r varies from $2a$ to $20a$. Four θ angles are shown as before: 0° , 60° , 120° , and 180° . The gray text background indicates scenarios when the receiver is geometrically shadowed by the sphere. (g) Impulse responses for the blended model output for $d_s = 2a$, $d_r = 4a$, (h) magnitude responses of HRTFs for $d_s = 1a$, $d_r = 20a$ computed from the proposed model (dashed lines) in comparison to the analytical solution (anal., solid lines) and the filter model (dotted lines) by Brown and Duda (1998). Note that the yellow dotted line is overlapped by the red dotted line because of the model’s symmetry about 150° . In addition, measured HRTFs of the KU 100 dummy head for 0° and 180° source-receiver angle from two data sets, the ARI (dashed, faint lines) and the SS2 (solid, faint lines), are plotted. Only frequencies above 0.1 kHz are shown.

the artificial spatial symmetry of Brown and Duda’s model at 120° and 180° (the overlap of the red and yellow dotted traces), which is non-existing in the analytical solution, is overcome by our model. The improved accuracy is demonstrated by the close alignment of the dashed green and yellow lines with the analytical solution (solid lines). The missing “bright spot” which is observed at 180° for the rigid sphere is apparent in both models. To understand the perceptual relevance of the bright spot for human heads, measured HRTFs from the Acoustics Research Institute (ARI; ARI HRTF-Database, 2025) and the Sound Sphere 2 (SS2; Warnecke et al., 2024) databases are also shown in Fig. 9(h). Both databases provide free-field equalized far-field HRTFs for the KU100 dummy head. At 180° , the measured responses exhibit higher magnitude than both filter models in the 1–5 kHz range, which then drop dramatically at higher frequency. In contrast, the bright spot effect for the rigid sphere is much more pronounced, caused by the perfect geometrical symmetry. At 0° , despite the strong peaks and notches at high frequencies because of pinna effects, the

overall magnitude of the measured HRTFs closely aligns with the analytical solution and the filter models.

B. Approximation error

The root mean square (RMS) error of the magnitude frequency response in dB, i.e., the logarithmically transformed magnitudes similar to the RMS logarithmic error, is used as the error metric for a systematic quantitative evaluation, defined as

$$e(m) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_m} \sum_{k=1}^{N_m} \left(20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{|F(f_k)|}{|F_{ref}(f_k)|} \right) \right)^2}, \quad (20)$$

where F is the frequency response to be compared with the reference response F_{ref} , and N_m is the number of frequency bins in the m th frequency band. The error is evaluated for angles from 0° to 180° in 5° increments for 35 one-third-octave bands between 10 Hz and 20 kHz.

Figure 10 presents the magnitude error of the diffracted field for the same source and receiver distances as in Figs. 9(a)–9(f).

FIG. 10. RMS error for the magnitude of the diffracted field in dB. The color bar runs from 0 dB to 6 dB, with the white color indicating 0 dB (no difference). The mean and maximum values across all frequency bands and angles for the low- and high-frequency range (separated at $ka = 1.6$) are indicated at the bottom of each panel. Max, maximum.

The mean and maximum error values across all frequency bands and angles for the low- and high-frequency approximation are displayed at the bottom of each panel. The low-frequency approximation demonstrates a uniformly good agreement, with mean RMS errors generally less than 1 dB. As shown previously in Figs. 9(a) and 9(c), when both d_r and d_s are small, larger deviations in the DC magnitude around 70° result in increased mean and maximum RMS error in the low-frequency range. These are residue errors because of order truncation as described in Sec. III, which can be compensated for by including the DC gain representation of high-order terms. For larger distances, the maximum errors are generally less than 6 dB.

The high-frequency model exhibits larger deviations compared to the low-frequency model. The RMS error shows a mean value of around 2 dB and a maximum value between 16.6 dB and 23.7 dB. The largest error concentrates in the transitional region between the illuminated zone and the shadowed zone, indicating the limitation of the proposed model in this region despite the associated modifications described in Sec. IV.

Given that for virtual acoustics applications and perceptual aspects, the accuracy of the total field appears more

FIG. 11. RMS error for the magnitude of the total field in dB. The color bar runs from 0 dB to 6 dB, with the white color indicating 0 dB (no difference). The mean and maximum values across all frequency bands and angles for the low- and high-frequency range (separated at $ka = 1.6$) are indicated at the bottom of each panel. Additionally, the mean and maximum values for a limited range of $\theta (\leq 160^\circ)$ are shown. Max, maximum.

relevant than that of the diffracted field alone, Fig. 11 shows the RMS error for the total field magnitude in the same format as in Fig. 10. Compared to Fig. 10, the mean RMS error is significantly reduced, falling below 0.5 dB for the low-frequency approximation and below 2 dB for the high-frequency approximation, with errors further decreasing with increasing distance. This reduction in the mean RMS error can be explained by the fact that the error is now evaluated on the magnitude of the total field, where the complex-valued incident field (without error) and (approximated) scattered field are superimposed [according to Eq. (3)]. The high-frequency error is primarily concentrated near 180° , where the model fails to reproduce the “bright spot” effect, resulting in maximum RMS error values of around or more than 10 dB. When excluding angles between 160° and 180° , the maximum RMS error generally falls below 5 dB, and the mean RMS error generally falls below 1 dB. Another region of elevated error is the transitional zone, consistent with observations previously shown in Fig. 10. Figure 11 also shows that when both d_r and d_s are small [Figs. 11(a) and 11(c)] and θ is large, the RMS error for the total field shows a reduction at the transition frequency. In these cases, the

RMS error is larger at lower frequencies because of the phase mismatch in the low-frequency filter representation relative to the analytical solution, as previously discussed for Fig. 4. Although phase correction was applied using all-pass filters, the residual phase errors in the low-frequency component lead to increased discrepancies when the diffracted field and the direct field are superimposed. The smaller phase error at the transition frequency results in better agreement with the analytical total field.

VI. DISCUSSION

A. General applicability of the filter model

We have demonstrated that (i) the overall shelving characteristic of the analytical solution for the diffracted field of a rigid sphere is accurately replicated by the suggested low-frequency approximation, (ii) the relative delay and amplitude difference between the two arrivals, as seen in Fig. 1, are effectively captured by the GA-based two-path representation for high frequencies, and (iii) the spectral characteristics of the two arrivals are reproduced by the modified proxy edge diffraction model to a large extent. The small mean RMS error for the total field indicates the general validity of our model for auralization purposes in virtual acoustics.

Our model significantly extends the applicability beyond that of the model by Sun *et al.* (1991) by using a much lower transition frequency when combining the low-frequency and high-frequency components and accounting for variable source and receiver positions. All possible geometrical relationships between the source, receiver, and the sphere are considered, and solutions for optimizing the accuracy of the filter representation for different cases are provided.

To approximate the high-frequency scattering in the illuminated zone of a sphere, previous studies proposed the simplification into two contributing components, one related to the specular reflection and one to the creeping or Franz waves around the sphere (e.g., Rheinstejn, 1968). Here, we simplified this concept to two distinct diffracted paths and extended it to also account for scattering in the shadowed zone. Compared to Wirler *et al.* (2021), where the shadowed and illuminated cases are modeled by different filter structures, our modified proxy edge diffraction model with heuristically derived edge configurations ensures the geometrical continuity in the model. The implementation of the fractional-order filters for the edge diffraction model could alternatively also be achieved by using appropriately parametrized simple filters to improve the computational efficiency of our model, especially considering that the modified diffraction model already applies a first-order low-pass filter for the longer path.

It is reasonable to expect that the scattering of cylinders would share certain features with that of spheres, given their geometrical similarity. In particular, Spratt and Abel (2008) highlighted a similar behavior of the diffracted field for the rigid cylinder regarding the two arrivals. Therefore, it is plausible to extend the GA-based high-frequency filter model proposed in this work to effectively capture the scattering behavior of cylinders as well.

B. Applicability for binaural rendering and source/receiver directivity modelling

The results for the total field in the case $d_s = 1a$ (or equivalently, $d_r = 1a$) are relevant to applications regarding modelling of HRTFs and binaural rendering. Our work reveals the physical basis underlying the shelving characteristics provided by the simple filters of Brown and Duda (1998) and Ewert *et al.* (2021), and we explicitly relate the filter parameters to the geometry and the spherical Bessel and Hankel functions. In particular, the cutoff frequency of the filters in the low-frequency model in our work is related to that in the two earlier studies.

For binaural rendering applications, reproducing the analytical DC gain is important especially for the near field, as near-field binaural cues are mainly present in the low-frequency range of the HRTF spectrum (Brungart and Rabinowitz, 1999), and the spherical head model is valid for large wavelengths. Compared to earlier studies such as Spagnol *et al.* (2017), our work provides a physics-based representation for the DC gain as well as the low-frequency component, which can be expressed with a single, universal formula for variable source and receiver distance. The low-frequency model in our work can be applied alone for extending the low-frequency response of near-field HRTFs from measurements, as well as for modelling general source or receiver directivity as in Ewert *et al.* (2021).

C. Limitations and future work

Although the suggested low-frequency approximation is clearly physics-based and shows exceptionally small errors in the total field, the high-frequency component of our model based on proxy infinite knife edges is functional and deviates from the geometrical and physical properties of the sphere. The modifications proposed in Sec. IV address these aspects by empirically fitting correction factors or setting bounds to the cutoff frequency for the edge diffraction filters. Although these adjustments benefit the performance of the model in this study, their general applicability might be further improved. A promising direction for future work would be to explore machine learning techniques to refine or generalize these correction factors. Alternatively, exploring diffraction models based on more realistic edge geometries, e.g., finite edges or three-sided barriers, might provide closer approximations to the scattering of the sphere and improve the overall fidelity of the high-frequency model.

Our GA-based two-path diffraction model also exhibits certain inherent limitations for θ angles approaching 180° . A straightforward solution is to modify the cutoff frequency of the edge diffraction filters for this region. Although the error in the high-frequency total field is particularly large near 180° , one consideration for virtual acoustics applications is that any object deviating from the perfect sphere, such as the human head, would not show the pronounced bright spot on the opposite side. Moreover, Wirler *et al.* (2021) reported that the reproduction of the bright spot using their filter model was perceived as exaggerated by human listeners. Thus, if the current model is used to approximate rounded but not perfectly symmetric objects in general, the

absence of a pronounced bright spot might actually better agree with the listener’s expectations.

For an efficient digital filter implementation applicable in virtual acoustics, the sigmoid-based magnitude and phase blending approach applied here for the error evaluation of the combined low- and high-frequency approximation may be impractical and could be replaced by better applicable time-domain crossover filters. Alternative methods should be explored for practical audio applications as future work. One approach is to use a crossover network, a technique commonly employed in audio signal processing to systematically merge low- and high-frequency components. Such a network would employ dedicated filters, such as Butterworth or Linkwitz-Riley (D’appolito, 1987) filters, to ensure minimal phase distortion and a more controlled transition between frequency bands.

VII. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

We presented a low-order filter-based model for the diffraction of a rigid sphere. The model is formulated for the diffracted field to have a better control over the approximation accuracy, whereas the total sound field can be easily computed by adding the direct field. Given the distinct wave properties across different frequencies, the low-frequency range is modeled using a low-order approximation for the analytical solution, whereas the high-frequency range is based on modelling two representative diffraction paths using geometrical acoustics. The main contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- We explicitly reformulated the analytical solution for sphere scattering into two structurally identical parts, which can be well described by high-pass or high-shelving filters in the low-frequency range. The proposed shelving filter structure for modelling the first three terms of the analytical solution produces a close match for the low-frequency range up to $ka = 1.6$ with a mean RMS error <1 dB of the diffracted field and <0.5 dB of the total field.
- The suggested low frequency approximation is valid for arbitrary source and receiver positions and explains the heuristic shelving filter approximations of the spherical head model for plane-wave incidence and receiver on the sphere. Our approximation offers a physics-based filter solution, which in isolation is also suited to introduce near-field effects in existing HRIR models or measurements.
- The suggested high-frequency approximation applies the concepts of GA, and utilizes a modified existing edge diffraction model for two propagation paths. This proxy edge representation is found valuable in the sense of reproducing the high-pass and low-pass behaviors of the two dominant arrivals in the time domain response of the analytical solution, except for the special case near and at 180° . The mean RMS error for the diffracted field is in the range of $1\sim3$ dB and for the total field below 2 dB or below 0.6 dB for angles smaller than 160° .
- Integrating the low- and high-frequency components of the model, a complete solution for the entire audible range

is obtained. A real-time implementation of the model with low-order IIR filters is possible, which would benefit applications such as binaural rendering, source and receiver directivity modelling, and object scattering simulation in architectural, room, and virtual acoustics.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

See the [supplementary material](#) for audio examples of two types of signals demonstrating the results of this study:

- (1) Male speech filtered with HRTFs generated by our model and by the analytical solution, for three source distances ($d_s = 2a, 4a,$ and $10a$) and three incidence angles ($0^\circ, 45^\circ,$ and 90° , with the right ear assumed to be at 0° and left ear at 180°).
- (2) Male speech filtered with the monaural output of the total field from our model and from the analytical solution, for two distance pairs ($d_r = d_s = 2a$ and $d_r = d_s = 10a$) and two incidence angles (one illuminated, one shadowed) for each distance pair.

For all simulations, distance-dependent attenuation is omitted to emphasize on the effect of diffraction.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The code for the model described in this study is openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231628>.

APPENDIX

Derivation of the analytical DC gain and phase response for an individual order in Eq. (5).

For the following function:

$$\Psi_n(k, d, a) = \sqrt{ik \cdot \frac{j_n'(ka)}{h_n^{(2)'}(ka)}} h_n^{(2)}(kd), \tag{A1}$$

we demonstrate how the DC gain and the phase response are determined for the example case of $n = 1$. We employ the recursion relation for the derivatives of the spherical Bessel and Hankel functions (Morse and Ingard, 1968),

$$j_n'(x) = -j_{n+1}(x) + \frac{n}{x} j_n(x), \tag{A2}$$

$$h_n^{(2)'}(x) = -h_{n+1}^{(2)}(x) + \frac{n}{x} h_n^{(2)}(x). \tag{A3}$$

Following that, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_1(k, d, a) &= \sqrt{ik \cdot \frac{j_1'(ka)}{h_1^{(2)}(ka)}} h_1^{(2)}(kd) = -e^{-ikd} \frac{kd-i}{k^2 d^2} \sqrt{ik \cdot \frac{-j_2(ka) + \frac{1}{ka} j_1(ka)}{-h_2(ka) + \frac{1}{ka} h_1(ka)}} \\ &= -e^{-ikd} \frac{kd-i}{k^2 d^2} \sqrt{ik \cdot \frac{-\left(\frac{3}{k^2 a^2} - 1\right) \frac{\sin(ka)}{ka} + \frac{3}{k^2 a^2} \cos(ka) + \frac{1}{ka} \left(\frac{\sin(ka)}{k^2 a^2} - \frac{\cos(ka)}{ka}\right)}{ie^{-ika} \frac{k^2 a^2 - 3ika - 3}{k^3 a^3} - \frac{1}{ka} e^{-ika} \frac{ka-i}{k^2 a^2}} \\ &= -e^{-ikd} \frac{kd-i}{k^2 d^2} \sqrt{ik \cdot \frac{2ka \cos(ka) + (k^2 a^2 - 2) \sin(ka)}{e^{-ika} (ik^2 a^2 + 2ka - 2i)}}. \end{aligned} \tag{A4}$$

For $k \rightarrow 0$, we can apply Taylor's expansion for the trigonometric functions,

$$\sin(ka) \approx ka - \frac{k^3 a^3}{6}, \tag{A5}$$

$$\cos(ka) \approx 1 - \frac{k^2 a^2}{2}, \tag{A6}$$

resulting in

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_1(k, d, a) &= -e^{-ikd} \frac{kd-i}{k^2 d^2} \sqrt{ik \cdot \frac{2ka \left(1 - \frac{k^2 a^2}{2}\right) + (k^2 a^2 - 2) \left(ka - \frac{k^3 a^3}{6}\right)}{e^{-ika} (ik^2 a^2 + 2ka - 2i)}} \\ &= -e^{-ikd} \frac{kd-i}{k^2 d^2} \sqrt{ik \cdot \frac{\frac{k^3 a^3}{3} - \frac{k^6 a^5}{6}}{e^{-ika} (ik^2 a^2 + 2ka - 2i)}} = -e^{-ik(d-(a/2))} \frac{kd-i}{d^2} \sqrt{\frac{i \left(\frac{a^3}{3} - \frac{k^3 a^5}{6}\right)}{e^{-ika} (ik^2 a^2 + 2ka - 2i)}}. \end{aligned} \tag{A7}$$

Calculating the absolute value of the result of Eq. (A7) for $k \rightarrow 0$, we get

$$|\Psi_1(k \rightarrow 0, d, a)| \rightarrow \left| \frac{i}{d^2} \sqrt{\frac{ia^3}{-6i}} \right| = \frac{1}{d^2} \sqrt{\frac{a^3}{6}}, \tag{A8}$$

which is the DC gain for $n = 1$ as given in Eq. (7).

For $n = 2$, instead of Eq. (A5) and Eq. (A6), we take the following into Eq. (A4):

$$\sin(ka) \approx ka - \frac{k^3 a^3}{6} + \frac{k^5 a^5}{120}, \tag{A9}$$

$$\cos(ka) \approx 1 - \frac{k^2 a^2}{2} + \frac{k^4 a^4}{24}, \tag{A10}$$

and repeat the other steps. For higher orders, we increase the number of terms in the Taylor series for the trigonometric functions accordingly.

Next, we present the derivation for the phase response of $\Psi_1(k, d, a)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \arg(\Psi_1(k, d, a)) &= \arg\left(\sqrt{ik \cdot \frac{j_1'(ka)}{h_1^{(2)}(ka)}} h_1^{(2)}(kd)\right) \\ &= \frac{\pi}{4} + \arg\left(-e^{-ikd} \frac{kd-i}{k^2 d^2} \sqrt{k \cdot \frac{2ka \cos(ka) + (k^2 a^2 - 2) \sin(ka)}{e^{-ika} (ik^2 a^2 + 2ka - 2i)}}\right) \\ &= \frac{\pi}{4} + \arg\left(-e^{-ikd} \frac{kd-i}{k^2 d^2}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \arg\left(k \left(2ka \cos(ka) + (k^2 a^2 - 2) \sin(ka)\right)\right) - \frac{1}{2} \arg\left(e^{-ika} (ik^2 a^2 + 2ka - 2i)\right) \\ &= \frac{\pi}{4} + \pi - kd + \arg\left(-\frac{kd-i}{k^2 d^2}\right) - \frac{1}{2} \left(-ka + \arg(ik^2 a^2 + 2ka - 2i)\right) \\ &= \frac{5\pi}{4} + k \left(\frac{a}{2} - d\right) - \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{kd}\right) - \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{k^2 a^2 - 2}{2ka}\right), \end{aligned} \tag{A11}$$

corresponding to Eq. (8).

- ¹Because the scattering of a rigid sphere is axisymmetric, the SH reduce to Legendre polynomials $P_n(\cos \theta)$. We use the term SH in reference to these axisymmetric expressions, whereas a full spherical harmonic formulation is possible *via* the addition theorem.
- ²Analysis of different distance combinations show that the error generally decreases as $(d_r \cdot d_s)/a^2$ increases.
- ³The apex point is the point where the shortest path for traveling from the source to the edge then from the edge to the receiver intersects with the edge.
- ⁴Note that two shadow boundaries are considered: the shadow boundary of the sphere and the shadow boundary of the proxy edge. In most cases within this study, the two are not identical.
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